

ILLIBERAL ATTITUDES AND THE JUSTIFICATION OF VIOLENCE: MISOGYNY'S ROLE IN UNDERMINING DEMOCRACY

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In recent years, the resurgence of authoritarian tendencies and political extremism across Central-Eastern Europe has prompted renewed scholarly attention to the sociocultural undercurrents that sustain such ideologies. Among these, misogyny has emerged as a potent ideological companion to authoritarianism and political violence. This study investigates the intersection of misogyny and political radicalism using data from the Joint European Values Study/World Values Survey (EVS/WVS 2024). Findings reveal that misogyny is a significant predictor of political violence in five countries and in the pooled regional model, while support for military rule consistently correlates with violent political attitudes across most cases. Democratic values are negatively associated with political violence. Socio demographic factors such as sex and age show limited and context-dependent effects, while income level is not a significant predictor. The results highlight the convergence of gender prejudice and authoritarianism as a destabilizing force in post-communist democracies, contributing to democratic backsliding and sociopolitical polarization.

Key words: misogyny; anti-gender mobilization; authoritarianism; gender prejudice; post-communist societies; political violence.

1 INTRODUCTION

The study investigates the interaction of misogyny and political violence in Central-Eastern Europe, a region marked by complex post-communist transitions that continue to influence present political developments and dynamics (Bădescu et al. 2025; Just and Morgado 2023), providing fertile ground for the rise of illiberalism. Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia were selected for their shared trajectory as post-

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communist states that joined the European Union (EU), undergoing similar processes of democratization and institutional reform. Their EU accession required the formal adoption of gender equality legislation, establishing a common policy framework, though its implementation and societal acceptance varied across countries (Sedelmeier 2012).

More recently, countries such as Hungary, Poland, and Romania have experienced concerning democratic backsliding (Puiu 2024). This erosion of democratic norms has coincided with the rise of populist-authoritarian parties that mobilize public sentiment through reframed national narratives (Bartok et al. 2024), and recent crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have further provided opportunities for populists to normalize their discourse (Haček 2014) or entrench their power (Tóth et al. 2025). These parties appeal to a configuration of attitudes, including distrust in global governance, hostility toward immigrants, traditionalist values, and religiosity, not as residual cultural traits, but as politically cultivated responses to perceived threats against national sovereignty and identity (Enyedi 2020; Jackson and Doerschler 2024). These attitudes, however, are not simply remnants of the past or population-wide orientation; rather, they are the product of right-wing populist-authoritarian parties' reframing of national discourse, such as through the harnessing of anti-Western resentment, the creation of a civilizationist anti-immigration platform, the revival of Christianity as a political identification, or the disempowerment of civil society. Within this transformed discursive environment, citizens can become more receptive to radical interpretations of political conflict. This kind of reframing contributes to the ideological grievances and identity-based anxieties that emerging research identifies as key drivers of public acceptance of political violence (Enyedi 2020). As such, individuals who perceive their in-group position threatened, including those who feel that gender hierarchies or gendered expectations are being contested, are more likely to legitimize violence as a form of political expression or defence (Kalmoe and Mason 2022; Ongun Baydar et al. 2025; Saptura 2019). This tendency is especially pronounced in contexts where authoritarian narratives normalize aggression and frame violence as necessary for preserving national or moral order. Political violence acceptance thus becomes a measurable indicator of democratic fragility and sociopolitical polarization. This ideological convergence between misogyny, authoritarianism, and political violence reflects a broader sociopolitical polarization in post-communist Europe (Guasti and Michal 2025; Vachudova 2020).

Against this backdrop, the present research investigates how gender prejudice intersects with political extremism, particularly in relation to public approval of political violence. By examining individual-level attitudes and demographic factors, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of sociopolitical polarization and democratic backsliding in post-communist Europe. The research is guided by the following question: *What individual-level attitudes and demographic factors are associated with the approval of political violence in the Central-Eastern European region?* The findings have implications for both academic theory and policy interventions aimed at safeguarding democratic norms and promoting gender equality in the region.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Political violence refers to the use of force or intimidation to achieve political objectives, encompassing a wide spectrum of actions, from state repression and

terrorism to civil unrest and insurgency (Sandler 2016). It is increasingly studied not only as a symptom of democratic erosion but also as a mechanism for consolidating authoritarian power. In democratic contexts, political violence often emerges in response to perceived threats to identity, status, or sovereignty. Auerbach and Petrova (2022) argue that unmet expectations and flawed democratization processes can fuel support for authoritarian actors and violent mobilization. This is particularly evident in regions experiencing democratic backsliding, where populist leaders may legitimize violence as a tool of political consolidation.

These mechanisms help explain why political violence intensifies under conditions of democratic backsliding, where institutional delegitimation and identity-based grievances converge. In this regard, social movement theory conceptualizes violence as a tactical escalation that emerges when institutional channels are blocked or delegitimized (Bosi and Demetriou 2015). In such contexts, actors may perceive violent repertoires as the only remaining means of exerting influence or signalling resistance (Bosi et al. 2014; della Porta 2013). This perspective highlights how political violence is not random but embedded within broader trajectories of contentious politics, where shifts from protest to militancy often reflect organizational dynamics and state responses (Bosi et al. 2014). Radicalization studies complement this view by emphasizing the role of identity-based grievances in fuelling support for violence. Research shows that feelings of status anxiety, perceived cultural displacement, and misogyny can become central drivers of radicalization, particularly when amplified in online echo chambers that reinforce exclusionary narratives (Bundtzen 2023; Fielitz and Thurston 2018). These digital spaces facilitate the circulation of anti-feminist and anti-LGBTQ discourses, which intersect with authoritarian ideologies to construct enemies and justify aggression (Ging 2019; Lewis et al. 2020).

Building on this foundation, the following literature review examines political violence throughout three interrelated domains: (1) feminist theories of misogyny and structural violence, (2) the role of misogyny in radicalization and extremist ideologies, and (3) the political dynamics of anti-gender discourse and democratic backsliding in Central-Eastern Europe, in order to better understand how gender prejudice functions as a driver of political violence acceptance in the region.

Misogynistic belief systems are constantly associated with violence both at individual and societal levels (Díaz and Valji 2019; Windisch 2023), explaining why gender prejudice becomes a powerful driver of political-violence acceptance in the region, with far-right and populist right movements frequently embedding and amplifying such ideologies (DeCook and Kelly 2022; Gentry 2022; O'Hanlon et al. 2024; Perliger et al. 2023; Švábová 2024; Jackson and Doerschler 2024). Moreover, the rise of far-right and populist right-wing parties and personalities in Central-Eastern Europe has coincided with the mainstreaming of anti-gender and anti-progressive rhetoric (Ćeriman and Vučković Juroš 2024; Darakchi 2019; Fábíán 2025; Grudzinska 2021; Matejková and Mihálik 2023; Muchova 2025; Neagu 2023; Norocel and Pettersson 2025; Stoencheva 2022; Svatonova 2021; Vučković Juroš et al. 2020) gaining traction in a region that has long struggled to address gender inequality and gender-based violence (Auerbach and Petrova 2022; Bochsler and Juon 2020; Einhorn and Sever 2003; Enyedi 2020; Fábíán 2010; Frunză 2006; Krizsán and Roggeband 2017; Kuhar and Paternotte 2017; Sedelmeier 2012). Hence, entrenched misogyny and anti-gender politics create fertile ground for the normalization of hostility, exclusion, and ultimately political violence. This dynamic aligns with longstanding feminist arguments that violence against women, particularly domestic violence, is not merely

interpersonal but deeply political, rooted in broader systems of gendered power and control (Marcus 1994, 2014; Pain 2014; Sloan-Lynch 2012).

Marcus (1994) draws parallels between domestic violence and terrorism, noting shared tactics such as psychological warfare, calculated intimidation, and the creation of persistent fear. Her later work (Marcus 2014) reframes domestic violence as a form of torture and terrorism, emphasizing its structural and ideological dimensions. Similarly, Sloan-Lynch (2012) and Pain (2014) argue that domestic violence enforces patriarchal domination through institutionally embedded terror, warranting recognition as a form of everyday terrorism. At the same time, violent misogyny and extremism often lack legal and conceptual clarity in the context of violent extremism prevention, despite growing evidence that misogyny functions as a core component of multiple extremist ideologies (Zimmerman 2024; O'Donnell and Shor 2022; Lockyer et al. 2025).

There is a need to recognize the full spectrum of male supremacist ideology and tailor prevention mechanisms focused on tackling misogynistic violence (O'Hanlon et al. 2024). Misogynist violence and specific manifestations, such as violent incels, need to be understood in the context of toxic and hegemonic masculinity. Addressing this requires challenging broad systems of oppression, such as cisheteropatriarchy and white supremacy, that underpin these ideologies and enable their spread (O'Hanlon et al. 2024). Therefore, this paper positions misogyny not simply as a personal bias but as a system of domination that legitimizes violence and sustains authoritarian social orders. Consistent with this direction, Edwards (2022) suggests that gender-based hate crimes often act as precursors to broader community violence and armed conflict, driven by efforts to reinforce male-dominated hierarchies. Therefore, the association between misogyny and violent extremism is documented to happen both at the individual and aggregate levels.

Individually, many perpetrators of violent extremism have a background of domestic violence and misogyny (Windisch 2023), while at an aggregate level, misogynistic beliefs and control over women are often explicit parts of the ideologies and tactics of prominent terrorist organizations and non-state armed groups (Díaz and Valji 2019). Moreover, research on radicalization shows that misogyny, racism and hypermasculinity fuel it, increasingly relying in recent years on online radicalization, gamified violence, revealing how the deep hatred of women acts as a gateway to broader extremist ideologies (Švábová 2024). These patterns underscore that misogynistic worldviews are not only produced within digital spaces but are also rooted in longer-term socialization processes that shape how individuals interpret hierarchy, authority, and belonging (Starowicz et al. 2025). These socialized beliefs form part of a broader ideological framework, with recent studies showing that misogynistic worldviews are closely tied to approval of violence (Ongun Baydar et al. 2025). Perceived status threats and injustice are also positively associated with approval of firearms, violence, and aggressive fantasies (Scaptura 2019) and with right-wing authoritarian attitudes (Pauwels and Heylen 2020).

Over the past decade, researchers have begun to unravel the crucial role that online spaces play in spreading and reinforcing misogynistic beliefs, with increasing literature on the relationship between online misogynist communities and far-right online spaces (O'Hanlon et al. 2024; Zimmerman 2024; Švábová 2024). These specific online spaces have been broadly studied as the *manosphere* (Farrell et al. 2019; DeCook and Kelly 2022; Perliger et al. 2023). The *manosphere* is characterized by Ribeiro et al. (2021) as a *conglomerate of Web-based misogynist movements focused on men's issues*. While comprising of a

number of different groups with varying ideologies, these communities are united in their misogynistic and male supremacists' beliefs, and their framing of men as victims of the current gender order (DeCook and Kelly 2022). These digital ecosystems not only reinforce anti-feminist and anti-democratic narratives but also serve as echo chambers for broader ideological grievances, being studied even as an overlooked security threat (Hunter and Jouenne 2021). Within the *manosphere* and the alt-right, communities frequently articulate deep dissatisfaction, frustration, and disorientation with modern society, sentiments that are often rooted in perceived declines in male status and the so-called 'crisis of masculinity' (Barcellona 2022).

This convergence of misogynistic rhetoric and socio-political discontent underscores how gendered resentment becomes a gateway to more expansive extremist worldviews. In Central-Eastern Europe, anti-gender ideology has become a key instrument of illiberal governance. Feminism, LGBTQ+ rights, and gender equality are increasingly framed as threats to national identity and traditional values (Bartok et al. 2024; Darakchi 2019; Fábíán 2025; Graff and Korolczuk 2022; Grudzinska 2021; Kuhar and Paternotte 2017). This discursive reframing matters for the study of political violence because it normalizes exclusion, legitimizes hostility toward women and queer communities, and lowers the threshold for public acceptance of coercive or punitive measures against them. Anti-gender narratives thus operate as boundary making devices that can translate into support for repressive policies, tolerance of harassment, and broader misogynistic attitudes that underpin the social acceptance of political violence (Stoenecheva 2022).

In Bulgaria, anti-gender rhetoric has been absorbed into heteronormative, religious, nationalist, and anti-feminist narratives. Notably, some women support these discourses, aligning themselves with patriarchal privilege and distancing themselves from other women (Constantinescu 2021a; Darakchi 2019). In Poland, it is framed as a defence of cultural and moral traditions against liberal elites (Grudzinska 2021). This anti-gender discourse is part of a broader neo-fascist ideology aimed at preserving cishetero-patriarchal dominance, often accompanied by xenophobic and anti-EU sentiments (Korolczuk 2020). In Hungary, the state's opposition to gender and sexual minorities reflects a broader push toward patriarchal control (Bartok et al. 2024; Fábíán 2025). Anti-gender rhetoric not only minimizes the structural nature of violence against women but also fosters resentment toward other marginalized groups, including immigrants, ethnic minorities, and LGBTQ+ communities (Edwards 2022; Ferber and Kimmel 2008; Piazza 2025; Van Hiel et al. 2020). Therefore, despite formal commitments to international gender equality norms, many post-communist states have struggled to implement effective protections for women due to cultural resistance, institutional inertia, and the depoliticization of gender violence (Einhorn and Sever 2003; Fábíán 2010; Krizsán and Roggeband 2017), framing the rejection of feminism as opposition to Western liberalism, reinforcing nationalist and civilizationist narratives (Frunză 2006; Enyedi 2020). Therefore, although EU accession led to the nominal adoption of gender equality laws (Sedelmeier 2012), enforcement remains uneven and politically contested (Fábíán 2010; Fábíán 2017; Krizsan and Roggeband 2019).

While the origins of "gender ideology" discourse can be traced to the Catholic Church in the 1990s, where it was used to resist growing international recognition of sexual and reproductive rights (Kuhar and Paternotte 2017), it has since been adopted and adapted by far-right and populist actors, becoming a central grievance in reactionary conservative ideology. This coincided with the accession of radical right-wing parties that worked to increase polarization

around gender equality, while at the same time ideological positioning has become a key factor in shaping attitudes toward gender roles, with traditionalist individuals increasingly aligning with radical right actors who challenge gender equality policies (Bartolomé Peral et al. 2024).

Moreover, the spread of anti-gender ideology and the lack of robust legal protections for women and LGBTQ communities have created space for the extreme right, enabling these actors to frame equality initiatives as external impositions and mobilize resistance against them (Bogaards and Petó 2022; Constantinescu 2021b; Constantinescu et al. 2025). Within this regional context, misogyny emerges not only as a persistent social prejudice but also as a politically consequential ideology. Prior research suggests that gender-based violence is not merely interpersonal but embedded in sociopolitical structures (Anderson and Umberson 2001; Johnson 1995, 2005; Marcus 1994, 2014; Pain 2014; Sloan-Lynch 2012), these dynamics are particularly salient in post-communist societies, where gendered violence is often depoliticized and dismissed in public discourse and policy (Fábián 2010). Resistance to legal interventions is at times justified by invoking fears of state intrusion reminiscent of communist regimes, contributing to weak enforcement and societal tolerance of certain forms of abuse (Fábián 2017; Rada 2014, 2020). At the same time, anti-gender ideology has gained traction across the region, often mobilized by right-wing populist actors to delegitimize progressive movements and reinforce patriarchal hierarchies (Darakchi 2019; Fábián 2025; Grudzinska 2021).

This ideological shift is not isolated, but forms part of a broader political strategy embraced by authoritarian and populist actors across the region. In countries like Poland, Hungary, and Bulgaria, anti-gender rhetoric has become a political tool to delegitimize progressive movements and consolidate power (Bartok et al. 2024; Grudzinska 2021; Stoencheva 2022). Such narratives not only minimize the structural nature of violence against women but also foster resentment toward other immigrants, ethnic minorities, and LGBTQ+ communities (Barcellona 2022; Edwards 2022; Ferber and Kimmel 2008; Ongun Baydar et al. 2025; Piazza 2025; Rottweiler et al. 2025; Scaptura 2019; Van Hiel et al. 2020; Windisch 2023). Similar phenomena are observable in other Central-Eastern European countries as well, such as Croatia (Čeriman and Vučković Juroš 2024; Vučković Juroš et al. 2020), Czech Republic (Matejková and Mihálik 2023; Muchova 2025; Svatonova 2021), Romania (Neagu 2023; Norocel and Pettersson 2025), Slovakia (Matejková and Mihálik 2023), and Slovenia (Kuhar 2017).

All these patterns present the Central-Eastern European region as a distinct and revealing context for examining the entanglement of gender politics and democratic backsliding. Despite formal commitments to international gender equality norms, many post-communist states have struggled to implement effective protections for women, often due to cultural resistance, institutional inertia, and the political instrumentalization of gender (Constantinescu et al. 2025; Einhorn and Sever 2003; Fábián 2010; Krizsán and Roggeband 2017; Puiu 2024). Nationalistic state leaders are argued to play a crucial role in inciting political violence through ethnic favouritism (Choi 2025). Furthermore Jungkunz, Fahley and Hino (2025) indicate that populist attitudes mediated by conspiratorial beliefs are linked to approval of political violence. Moreover, rejecting feminism and progressive causes is frequently framed as opposition to Western liberalism, reinforcing nationalist and civilizationist narratives (Enyedi 2020; Frunză 2006; Šteger 2024). Within this ideological environment, misogyny forms part of an exclusionary, hierarchical worldview that can make political violence appear justified, necessary, or even virtuous. This study now turns to

empirical analysis to assess how these dynamics manifest in individual-level acceptance of political violence across the region.

3 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The present study draws on statistical analysis of the Joint European Values Study/World Values Survey dataset, using data collected between 2017 and 2022 (EVS/WVS 2024). The dataset merges the common elements of the 2017 European Values Study with the seventh wave of the World Values Survey, providing a harmonized and cross-nationally comparable foundation for examining political and social attitudes.

The analysis focuses on Central-Eastern European member states of the European Union: Bulgaria (BG, N=1558), Croatia (HR, N=1487), Czech Republic (CZ, N=3011), Hungary (HU, N=1514), Poland (PL, N=1352), Romania (RO, N=2870), Slovakia (SV, N=2632), Slovenia (SL, N=1075). These cases offer a coherent regional cluster marked by shared post-communist trajectories, similar institutional legacies, and parallel contemporary debates over gender, democracy, and political violence. The research will evaluate the following hypotheses:

H1: Higher levels of misogynistic attitudes are positively correlated with individuals' approval of political violence in the Central-Eastern European region.

H2: Men are more likely than women to approve of political violence Central-Eastern European region.

H3: Support for authoritarian forms of governance is positively associated with the justification of political violence in the Central-Eastern European region.

H4: The relationships proposed in H1 and H3 hold across both at the aggregate level of the full dataset and within individual country samples.

H5: Respondents' income levels do not significantly influence their views on political violence.

H6: Younger respondents are more likely to approve of political violence in the Central-Eastern European region.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable is *Justifiable: Political Violence*. This variable captures respondents' willingness to approve the use of political violence. It is based on the survey item "Please tell me for each of the following statements whether you think it can always be justified, never be justified, or something in between...Political violence." Responses are measured on a 10-points scale ranging from "Never justifiable" to "Always justifiable," allowing for the assessment of varying degrees of acceptance. Higher scores indicate greater approval of political violence as a legitimate political tool, while lower scores reflect stronger rejection of such actions.

Independent variables

The main independent variable is Misogynistic attitudes. This is a composite index constructed from four survey items reflecting traditional gender role beliefs. The items include:

1. "Men should have more rights to a job than women." (factor loading: .676)
2. "Men make better political leaders than women do." (factor loading: .816)
3. "University is more important for a boy than for a girl." (factor loading: .760)
4. "Men make better business executives than women do." (factor loading: .855).

These items were subjected to factor analysis, yielding a single factor that explains 60.8% of the variance (eigenvalue = 2.43). The resulting scale demonstrates good internal consistency (Cronbach’s Alpha = .759). Factor scores were extracted using regression (REGR factor score) and used as the main predictor in H1 and H4. The other independent variables are:

Sex: A binary variable indicating the respondent’s sex (0 = Female, 1 = Male), used to test H2.

Age: A continuous variable representing the respondent’s age in years, used to test H6.

Income Level: Measured using decile-based on a national income scale, used to test H5.

Authoritarian Governance Preferences variables, each measured on a five-point Likert scale; these variables assess support for different political systems and are used to test H3 and H4:

1. Having a strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections.
2. Having experts, not government, make decisions according to what they think is best for the country.
3. Having the army rule the country.
4. Having a democratic political system.

4 RESULTS

A correlation analysis was conducted to examine H1, the relationship between misogynistic attitudes and the approval of political violence. The analysis utilized extracted factor scores representing misogyny as the independent variable, and the item *Justifiable: Political violence* as the dependent variable. Results indicated a statistically significant, though modest, positive correlation across the full sample ($r = .147, p < .01$), suggesting that higher levels of misogyny are associated with greater justification of political violence. To assess cross-national consistency, the correlation was also calculated separately for each country in the dataset. As shown in Table 1, the relationship was statistically significant in all observed countries except Slovenia, where the correlation was not significant ($r = .049, ns$). The strongest correlation was observed in Bulgaria ($r = .166, p < .01$), followed by Hungary ($r = .127, p < .01$) and Romania ($r = .116, p < .01$). These findings support H1, that misogyny is positively associated with approval of political violence across most national contexts in the Central-Eastern European region.

TABLE 1: CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS (R), VARIABLES: REGR FACTOR SCORE (MISOGYNY), JUSTIFIABLE: POLITICAL VIOLENCE, JOINT EVS-WVS 2017-2022

Country	Coefficient
Bulgaria	.166**
Croatia	.097**
Czech Republic	.114**
Hungary	.127**
Poland	.079*
Romania	.116**
Slovakia	.085**
Slovenia	.049 (ns)
ALL	.147**

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), ns = not significant.

To test H2: men are more likely than women to justify political violence, a correlation analysis was conducted using sex and *Justifiable: Political violence* as

the dependent variable. Across the full sample, the analysis revealed a statistically significant but weak negative correlation ($r = -.050, p < .01$), indicating that male respondents are slightly more inclined than female respondents to approve of political violence. Country-level analyses yielded mixed results. As shown in Table 2, statistically significant correlations were observed in five of the eight countries: Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia, and Poland (though Poland’s result was not statistically significant). The strongest correlation was found in Slovakia ($r = -.075, p < .01$). In contrast, Bulgaria, Romania, and Slovenia did not show significant associations. These findings suggest that while the overall trend supports H2, the strength and significance of the relationship vary across national contexts.

TABLE 2: CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS (R), VARIABLES: SEX, JUSTIFIABLE: POLITICAL VIOLENCE, JOINT EVS-WVS 2017-2022

Country	Coefficient
Bulgaria	-.040 (ns)
Croatia	-.075*
Czech Republic	-.050*
Hungary	-.071*
Poland	-.053 (ns)
Romania	-.035 (ns)
Slovakia	-.075**
Slovenia	-.022 (ns)
ALL	-.050**

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), ns = not significant.

Regression analyses were conducted to test H3 and H4, using *Justifiable: Political Violence* as the dependent variable and including predictors such as misogyny, support for authoritarian governance, sex, age, and income. The model was run for Bulgaria (BG), Croatia (HR), Czech Republic (CZ), Hungary (HU), Poland (PL), Romania (RO), Slovakia (SK), and Slovenia (SI), as well as a pooled regional model (ALL). Standardized regression coefficients (β) and model fit statistics are reported below.

TABLE 3: STANDARDIZED REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS (β), DEPENDENT VARIABLE: JUSTIFIABLE: POLITICAL VIOLENCE, JOINT EVS-WVS 2017-2022

Predictor	BG	HR	CZ	HU	PL	RO	SK	SL	ALL
REGR factor score (Misogyny)	.136*	.105*	.037 (ns)	.073 (ns)	.148*	.170*	-.012 (ns)	.025 (ns)	.164**
Having a strong leader	-.027 (ns)	.037 (ns)	.170*	.090 (ns)	.119 (ns)	-.179*	.429**	.076 (ns)	.044*
Having experts make decisions	-.025 (ns)	-.041 (ns)	-.116 (ns)	-.006 (ns)	-.046 (ns)	-.089 (ns)	-.248*	.039 (ns)	-.104**
Having the army rule	.109*	.014 (ns)	.473**	.178*	.052 (ns)	.182*	.539**	.338**	.206**
Having a democratic political system	-.438**	-.083 (ns)	-.269*	-.138*	-.117 (ns)	-.332*	-.372**	-.166*	-.306**
Sex	-.088 (ns)	-.165*	-.255*	-.082 (ns)	-.114 (ns)	.091 (ns)	-.388*	-.029 (ns)	-.108*
Age	-.005 (ns)	-.005*	-.013**	-.005*	-.013*	-.019*	-.002 (ns)	-.002 (ns)	-.009**
Scale of incomes	-.022 (ns)	-.019 (ns)	-.023 (ns)	-.008 (ns)	-.006 (ns)	.014 (ns)	.031 (ns)	.001 (ns)	-.018*
Model R ²	.102	.023	.089	.049	.050	.089	.193	.073	.76

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), ns = not significant.

Model fit statistics (R^2) varied across countries, with the highest explanatory power in Slovakia ($R^2 = .193$) and Bulgaria ($R^2 = .102$), while Croatia and Poland showed relatively low fit ($R^2 = .023$ and $.050$, respectively). The pooled model demonstrated strong overall fit ($R^2 = .76$), indicating that the combined

predictors offer substantial explanatory value when applied across the region. Misogyny emerged as a statistically significant positive predictor of political violence in four of the eight countries: Bulgaria (.136), Croatia (.105), Poland (.148), Romania (.170). The strongest effect was observed in Romania ($\beta = .170$, $p < .05$) and in the regional model ($\beta = .164$, $p < .01$), reinforcing the hypothesis that gendered resentment is a meaningful ideological driver of political violence. However, the lack of significance in countries like Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia, and Slovenia indicates that this relationship may be mediated by national context, cultural norms, or differing levels of gender equality and political polarization.

Support for authoritarian governance was consistently associated with higher justification of political violence. The variable "Having the army rule" was a significant positive predictor in Bulgaria (.109), Czech Republic (.473), Hungary (.178), Romania (.182), Slovakia (.539), and Slovenia (.338). Inversely, support for a democratic political system is a significant negative predictor in the same six countries: Bulgaria (-.438), Czech Republic (-.269), Hungary (-.138), Romania (-.332), Slovakia (-.372), and Slovenia (-.166), findings suggesting that democratic commitment acts as a protective factor against the endorsement of political violence, aligning with broader literature on democratic norms and political tolerance. Moreover, these results suggest that authoritarian attitudes, especially those favouring military control, are strongly linked to violent political sentiments across the region, possibly reflecting a broader acceptance of coercive state power. Interestingly, *Having a strong leader* yielded mixed results. It was significant in the Czech Republic ($\beta = .170$, $p < .05$) and Slovakia ($\beta = .429$, $p < .01$), but not in most other countries. This may indicate that the appeal of strongman leadership varies across national contexts and is not uniformly linked to violence approval.

In contrast, *Having experts make decisions* was negatively associated with political violence justification in Slovakia ($\beta = -.248$, $p < .05$) and in the pooled model ($\beta = -.104$, $p < .01$), suggesting that technocratic governance is perceived as a stabilizing force that discourages violent political expression.

Testing H6, age showed a small but consistent negative association with political violence justification in most countries and in the pooled model ($\beta = -.009$, $p < .01$), indicating that younger individuals are slightly more inclined to endorse political violence. This may reflect generational differences in political engagement or exposure to radicalizing content online.

Income (H5), however, did not emerge as a significant predictor in most models, with only a weak negative association in the pooled analysis ($\beta = -.018$, $p < .05$). Although other studies found that the economic background can influence far right political views (Plešivčák 2023) our results suggest that economic status may be less influential than ideological and identity-based factors in shaping attitudes toward political violence.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

These study findings are aligned with the body of research that show that misogyny, when situated within broader political and ideological orientations, plays a meaningful, though complex, role in shaping public support for political violence (Hawley 2023; Matsunaga 2025; Parsons 2023), and suggest misogyny to be a component of broader antidemocratic tendencies, that consolidates

support for political violence (Díaz and Valji 2019; Gentry 2022; Windisch 2023; Wintemute et al. 2023).

Across the region, misogynistic attitudes show a consistent positive association with the justification of political violence, with Slovenia as the only exception. Although these correlations are modest in magnitude, they indicate that misogyny functions as part of a wider attitudinal constellation linked to hierarchical worldviews, illiberal values, and diminished commitment to democratic norms. While misogyny manifests at a social and individual level, a specific focus on the different violent expressions of misogyny in the private and public spheres in the region is necessary, as misogyny may be a part of a larger set of attitudes that are also likely to predict the justification of political violence.

Gender differences in support for political violence are present but limited. Men are somewhat more likely than women to justify political violence, yet the effect varies across national contexts and remains relatively small. These patterns underscore that gender, while relevant, is not the dominant demographic factor shaping attitudes toward political violence, such as in previous studies (Bardall et al. 2020).

The country-level analysis revealed further nuances (Hypothesis 4). Statistically significant correlations were observed in five of the eight countries, with the strongest effect in Slovakia. However, in countries such as Bulgaria, Romania, and Slovenia, the relationship was not significant, suggesting that gendered attitudes toward political violence may be shaped by national context, cultural norms, or differing levels of political polarization. These variations underscore the importance of disaggregating cross-national data and avoiding over-generalisation. They also point to the need for more complex models that account for intersecting factors such as education, political ideology, exposure to violence, and media consumption.

Misogynistic attitudes and the tendency to justify political violence are significantly correlated on regional and most country levels (with Slovenia being the exception) (Hypothesis 4). Furthermore, at the level of region, misogynistic attitudes, and a preference for authoritarian forms of government are shown to be predictors of a justification of political violence (Hypothesis 3). However, when looking at individual country-level data, the findings are not conclusive.

Misogyny and a preference towards more authoritarian forms of government are statistically significant, alongside the demographic factors (apart from education). The results would indicate that holding misogynistic or anti-democratic opinions, as well as being a younger man in lower economic strata are predictors for justifying political violence. At the same time, this does not hold across all countries' contexts. Gender alone is only significantly correlated to the justification of political violence in half of the country contexts. Income seems to have little to no significant predictive power across individual countries, while gender and age seem to be more relevant demographic factors (Hypotheses 2, 5 and 6). Preference towards certain forms of government seems to be a relevant factor across most countries' contexts, though with the caveat being those specific preferences, such as one's attitude towards army rule and democracy, seem to be relevant across most states (Hypothesis 3). Misogyny was only statistically significant across half of the cases, with those indicating a positive relation to political violence.

To conclude, the findings should be interpreted in the context of the rise of populist-authoritarian parties that mobilize anti-gender, anti-democratic, and

nationalist discourses (Darakchi 2019; Enyedi 2020; Grudzinska 2021) across Europe, that frame national identity in opposition to liberal democratic norms, often using misogyny and militarism as ideological tools. The present study shows that these discourses are not only politically salient but also predictive of public support for political violence, underscoring the need to treat misogynist ideology as a central component of extremist mobilization.

By foregrounding the gendered dimensions of radicalization, the analysis highlights how addressing misogyny is essential for strengthening democratic resilience and developing more effective prevention strategies. Studying and recognizing the full extent of the issue and the dangers presented facilitates the creation and adoption of targeted measures that aim to curb extremist violence. Furthermore, recognizing the widespread and indiscriminate nature of extremist violence and misogyny opens researchers and policy makers to taking specific actions and approaches that aim to tackle the underlying societal ills that bring about such attitudes, as well as those that directly target the would-be perpetrators of political violence.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, Kristin L. and Debra Umberson. 2001. "Gendering violence: masculinity and power in men's accounts of domestic violence." *Gender and Society* 15 (3): 358–380.
- Auerbach, Kiran and Bilyana Petrova. 2022. "Authoritarian or simply disillusioned? Explaining democratic scepticism in central and eastern Europe." *Political Behaviour* 44 (4): 1959–1983.
- Bădescu, Gabriel, Daniela Angi, Jozsef Benedek and Sorana Constantinescu. 2025. "Historical legacies and their impact on human capital: comparing regions within Romania." *East European Politics and Societies* 39 (1): 3–26.
- Barcellona, Marta. 2022. "Incel violence as a new terrorism threat: A brief investigation between alt-right and manosphere dimensions." *Sortuz: Oñati Journal of Emergent Socio-Legal Studies* 11 (2): 2.
- Bardall, Gabrielle, Elin Bjarnegård and Jennifer M. Piscopo. 2020. "How is political violence gendered? disentangling motives, forms, and impacts." *Political Studies* 68 (4): 916–935.
- Bartok, Szilard, Xenia Caramete and Dana Rosca. 2024. "Comparative examination of the discourse of far-right parties on social media: Fidesz (Hungary) and Fratelli d'Italia (Italy)." *Research in Social Change* 16 (2): 57–80.
- Bartolomé Peral, Edurne, María Silvestre, Ayauzhan Kamatayeva and Bogdan Voicu. 2024. "Women, antifeminism, and platforms: the discourses of misogyny value change regarding gender roles and backlash in Europe: is gender a new polarization element?" *International Journal of Communication* 18 (August): 0.
- Bochsler, Daniel and Andreas Juon. 2020. "Authoritarian footprints in central and eastern Europe." *East European Politics* 36 (2): 167–187.
- Bogaards, Matthijs and Andrea Pető. 2022. "Gendering de-democratization: gender and illiberalism in post-communist Europe." *Politics and Governance* 10 (4): 1–5.
- Bosi, Lorenzo and Chares Demetriou. 2015. Social movements and political violence. In *International encyclopaedia of the social & behavioural sciences*, 2nd Edition, eds. Wright, James D., 430–436. London: Elsevier.
- Bosi, Lorenzo, Chares Demetriou and Stefan Malthaner. 2014. A contentious politics approach to the explanation of radicalization. In *Dynamics of political violence*, eds. Demetriou, Chares and Lorenzo Bosi, 3–38. London: Routledge.
- Bundtzen, Sara. 2023. *Misogynistic pathways to radicalisation: recommended measures for platforms to assess and mitigate online gender-based violence*. Institute for Strategic Dialogue. Available at <https://www.isdglobal.org/publication/misogynistic-pathways-to-radicalisation-recommended-measures-for-platforms-to-assess-and-mitigate-online-gender-based-violence>.

- Ćeriman, Jelena and Tanja Vučković Juroš. 2024. "From gender re-traditionalizations to anti-gender mobilizations: care for family in Serbia and Croatia." *East European Politics and Societies* 38 (2): 662–681.
- Choi, Seung-Whan. 2025. "Nationalism and political violence." *Oxford Research Encyclopaedia of International Studies*. Available at <https://oxfordre.com/internationalstudies/display/10.1093/acrefore/9780190846626.001.0001/acrefore-9780190846626-e-869>.
- Constantinescu, Sorana. 2021a. "How does the Internalization of misogyny operate: a theoretical approach with European examples." *Research in Social Change* 13 (1): 120–128.
- Constantinescu, Sorana. 2021b. "Romania queer in context European 2021: Analiza istoriei recente și a traiectoriilor posibile." In *Secolul XXI. Istorie Recentă Și Futurologie*, ed. Cistelean, Alex, 217–239. Bucuresti: Editura Cartier.
- Constantinescu, Sorana, Carina Puiu and Tudorina Mihai. 2025. "'Cade Una, Sărim Toate!' Politicile de Gen În România În Timpul Mandatelor Lui Klaus Iohannis." In *Epoca Klaus Iohannis? România Între 2014 Și 2025*, eds. Bâlici, Mihnea, Anca Bîrnoiu, Veronica Lazăr, Catrinel Rădoi and Vali Stan, 381–402. Cluj-Napoca: Tact.
- Darakchi, Shaban. 2019. "'The western feminists want to make us gay': nationalism, heteronormativity, and violence against women in Bulgaria in times of 'anti-gender campaigns.'" *Sexuality & Culture* 23 (4): 1208–1229.
- DeCook, Julia R. and Megan Kelly. 2022. "Interrogating the 'incel menace': assessing the threat of male supremacy in terrorism studies." *Critical Studies on Terrorism* 15 (3): 706–726.
- della Porta, Donatella. 2013. *Clandestine Political Violence*. Cambridge Studies in Contentious Politics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Díaz, Pablo Castillo and Nahla Valji. 2019. "Symbiosis of misogyny and violent extremism: new understandings and policy implications." *Journal of International Affairs* 72 (2): 37–56.
- Edwards, Christie. 2022. "Combating incels: addressing misogynistic violence as an early warning indicator of escalating violence and armed conflict." *Loyola University Chicago International Law Review* 19 (1): 1–25.
- Einhorn, Barbara and Charlotte Sever. 2003. "Gender and Civil Society in Central and Eastern Europe." *International Feminist Journal of Politics* 5 (2): 163–190.
- Enyedi, Zsolt. 2020. "Right-Wing Authoritarian Innovations in Central and Eastern Europe." *East European Politics* 36 (3): 363–377.
- EVS/WVS. 2024. "Joint EVS/WVS 2017-2022 Dataset (Joint EVS/WVS)." Version 5.0.0. Tilburg: GESIS.
- Fábián, Katalin. 2010. "Introduction: The politics of domestic violence in postcommunist Europe and Eurasia." In *Domestic violence in postcommunist states: local activism, national policies, and global forces*, ed. Fábián, Katalin, 1–42. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Fábián, Katalin. 2017. "The politics of domestic violence in central Europe: international and domestic contestations." In *Global responses to domestic violence*, eds. Eve S. Buzawa and Carl G. Buzawa, 125–149. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Fábián, Katalin. 2025. "Gender-based violence in contemporary Hungary: progress in recognition and backlash in policies." *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society* 4 (1).
- Farrell, Tracie, Miriam Fernandez, Jakub Novotny and Harith Alani. 2019. "Exploring misogyny across the manosphere in Reddit." *Proceedings of the 10th ACM Conference on Web Science* (New York, NY, USA), WebSci 2019, 26 June, 87–96.
- Ferber, Abby L. and Michael S. Kimmel. 2008. "The gendered face of terrorism." *Sociology Compass* 2 (3): 870–887.
- Fielitz, Maik and Nick Thurston (eds.). 2018. *Post-digital cultures of the far right: online actions and offline consequences in Europe and the US*. Bielefeld: Transcript Verlag.
- Frunză, Mihaela. 2006. "Who's afraid of feminism in Romania? Misconceptions, prejudices, stereotypes." *Journal for the study of religions and ideologies* 5 (14): 14.
- Gentry, Caron E. 2022. "Misogynistic terrorism: it has always been here." *Critical studies on terrorism* 15 (1): 209–224.
- Ging, Debbie. 2019. "Alphas, betas, and incels: theorizing the masculinities of the manosphere." *Men and masculinities* 22 (4): 638–657.

- Graff, Agnieszka and Elżbieta Korolczuk. 2022. "Anti-gender campaigns as a reactionary response to neoliberalism." *European journal of women's studies* 29 (1_suppl): 150S–157S.
- Grudzinska, Anna. 2021. Make misogyny great again. "Anti-gender" politics in Poland. In *Current populism in Europe*, eds. Mejstřík, Martin and Vladimír Handl, 23–36. Prague: Heinrich Böll Stiftung.
- Guasti, Petra and Aleš Michal. 2025. "Polarization and democracy in central Europe." *Politics and Governance* 13 (June).
- Haček, Miro. 2014. "(Dis)trust into political institutions and conspiracy theories: case of Slovenia." *Journal of comparative politics* 17 (2): 5–16.
- Hunter, Kyleanne and Emma Jouenne. 2021. "All women belong in the kitchen, and other dangerous tropes: online misogyny as a national security threat." *Journal of advanced military studies* 12 (1): 57–85.
- Jackson, Pamela Irving and Peter Doerschler. 2024. "What drives support for authoritarian populist parties in eastern and central Europe?" *International sociology* 39 (6): 606–630.
- Johnson, Michael P. 1995. "Patriarchal terrorism and common couple violence: two forms of violence against women." *Journal of marriage and family* 57 (2): 283–294.
- Johnson, Michael P. 2005. "Domestic violence: it's not about gender—or is it?" *Journal of marriage and family* 67 (5): 1126–1130.
- Jungkunz, Sebastian, Robert A. Fahey and Airo Hino. 2025. "Populist attitudes, conspiracy beliefs and the justification of political violence at the US 2020 elections." *Political studies* 73 (2): 592–611.
- Just, Petr and Nuno Morgado. 2023. "Reviving traumas and grievances: geopolitical codes and political culture in central Europe." *Journal of comparative politics* 16 (2): 51–66.
- Kalmoe, Nathan P. and Lillian Mason. 2022. *Radical American partisanship: mapping violent hostility, its causes, and the consequences for democracy*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Korolczuk, Elżbieta. 2020. "The fight against "gender" and "LGBT ideology": new developments in Poland." *European journal of politics and gender* 3 (1): 165–167.
- Krizsán, Andrea and Conny Roggeband. 2017. Introduction: the gender politics of domestic violence reforms in central and eastern Europe. In *The gender politics of domestic violence: feminists engaging the state in central and eastern Europe*, eds. Krizsán, Andrea and Conny Roggeband, 1–17. New York: Routledge.
- Kuhar, Roman. 2017. Changing gender several times a day: the anti-gender movement in Slovenia. In *Anti-gender campaigns in Europe: mobilizing against equality*, eds. Kuhar, Roman and David Paternotte, 215–232. London: Rowman & Littlefield International.
- Kuhar, Roman and David Paternotte (eds.). 2017. "Gender ideology" in movement: Introduction. In *Anti-gender campaigns in Europe: mobilizing against equality*, eds. Kuhar, Roman and David Paternotte, 1–22. London: Rowman & Littlefield International.
- Lewis, Seth C., Rodrigo Zamith and Mark Coddington. 2020. "Online harassment and its implications for the journalist–audience relationship." *Digital Journalism* 8 (8).
- Lockyer, Demeter, Michael Halpin and Finlay Maguire. 2025. "The emergence of the incel community as a misogyny-motivated terrorist threat." *Terrorism and political violence* 37 (3): 369–385.
- Marcus, Isabel. 1994. "Reframing "domestic violence": terrorism in the home." In *The public nature of private violence*, ed. Fineman, Martha Albertson, 11–35. New York: Routledge.
- Marcus, Isabel. 2014. "Reframing domestic violence as terrorism or torture." *Collection of Papers, Faculty of Law, Niš* 67 (13): 13–24.
- Matejková, Alexandra and Jaroslav Mihálik. 2023. "Against gender: the anti-gender movements and the socio-cultural and moral deconstructions in Europe." *Human affairs* 33 (1): 1–12.
- Muchova, Adela. 2025. "Power dynamics and gender discourse." *Religion and gender* 15 (2): 140–161.
- Neagu, Florina-Marieta. 2023. "Women's rights under threat: an analysis of the anti-"gender ideology" legislation in contemporary Romania." Master thesis, University of Tromsø. Available at <https://munin.uit.no/handle/10037/29554>.
- Norocel, Ov Cristian and Katarina Pettersson. 2025. "Anti-gender politics in Finland and Romania." *European Journal of Politics and Gender* 8 (1): 189–206.

- O'Donnell, Catharina and Eran Shor. 2022. "This is a political movement, friend: why "incels" support violence." *The British journal of sociology* 73 (2): 336–351.
- O'Hanlon, Robin, Frederick L. Altice, Roy Ka-Wei Lee, et al. 2024. "Misogynistic extremism: a scoping review." *Trauma, violence & abuse* 25 (2): 1219–1234.
- Ongun Baydar, Huriye, Veysi Baydar and Gülay Günay. 2025. "How sexism affects violence against women: The mediating role of misogyny." *Türk dünyası kadın araştırmaları dergisi* 4 (6): 6.
- Pain, Rachel. 2014. "Everyday terrorism: connecting domestic violence and global terrorism." *Progress in human geography* 38 (4): 531–550.
- Pauwels, Lieven J. R. and Ben Heylen. 2020. "Perceived group threat, perceived injustice, and self-reported right-wing violence: an integrative approach to the explanation right-wing violence." *Journal of interpersonal violence* 35 (21–22): 4276–4302.
- Perliger, Arie, Catherine Stevens and Eviane Leidig. 2023. *Mapping the ideological landscape of extreme misogyny*. ICCT Research Paper. The Hague: International Centre for Counterterrorism (ICCT). Available at <https://icct.nl/publication/mapping-ideological-landscape-extreme-misogyny>.
- Piazza, James A. 2025. "Incel beliefs and support for political violence among U.S. males: the mediating effects of masculinity stress, aggression, outgroup hate, and illiberalism." *Crime & delinquency* 0 (0): 1–32.
- Plešivčák, Martin. 2023. "How electoral geography can help in struggle with the far right: example of Slovakia." *Journal of comparative politics* 16 (1): 110–125.
- Puiu, Carina Ștefania. 2024. "Between rights and rhetoric: the erosion of women's and LGBTQ+ rights in Romania, Hungary and Poland." *Research in social change* 16 (2): 39–56.
- Rada, Cornelia. 2014. "Violence against women by male partners and against children within the family: prevalence, associated factors, and intergenerational transmission in Romania, a cross-sectional study." *BMC public health* 14 (1): 129.
- Rada, Cornelia. 2020. "Violence, communication, and satisfaction among middle-aged adults and older people from Romania." *Humanities and social sciences communications* 7 (1): 1–12.
- Ribeiro, Manoel Horta, Jeremy Blackburn, Barry Bradlyn, et al. 2021. "The evolution of the manosphere across the web." *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on web and social media* 15 (May): 196–207.
- Rottweiler, Bettina, Caitlin Clemmow and Paul Gill. 2025. "A Common psychology of male violence? Assessing the effects of misogyny on intentions to engage in violent extremism, interpersonal violence and support for violence against women." *Terrorism and political violence* 37 (3): 287–312.
- Sandler, Todd. 2016. "Political violence: an introduction." *Public Choice* 169 (3): 161–170.
- Scaptura, Maria N. 2019. "Masculinity threat, misogyny, and the celebration of violence in white men." Master Thesis, Virginia Tech. Available at <http://hdl.handle.net/10919/93239>.
- Sedelmeier, Ulrich. 2012. "Is Europeanisation through conditionality sustainable? lock-in of institutional change after EU accession." *West European politics* 35 (1): 20–38.
- Sloan-Lynch, Jay. 2012. "Domestic abuse as terrorism." *Hypatia* 27 (4): 774–790.
- Starowicz, Anna, Anna Wnuk, Tomasz Oleksy, Mikołaj Szołtysek and Małgorzata Gambin. 2025. "Family support for patriarchal culture and misogyny in Poland: moderating factors." *Translational Issues in Psychological Science* (US), ahead of print.
- Šteger, Tine. 2024. "The analysis of prevailing conspiracy theories in central and eastern Europe." *Journal of Comparative Politics* 17 (1): 69–85.
- Stoencheva, Jullietta. 2022. "The manosphere travels east: constructing misogynist social identities on a Bulgarian online platform." Master Thesis, Malmö University. Available at <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:mau:diva-53079>.
- Švábová, Barbora. 2024. "Misogyny as a key driver for right-wing extremists: Is it all about hate for women?" Master Thesis, Univerzita Karlova. Available at <https://dspace.cuni.cz/handle/20.500.11956/195304>.
- Svatonova, Eva. 2021. "'Gender activists will kidnap your kids': The construction of feminist and LGBT+ rights activists as modern folk devils in Czech anti-gender campaigns." In *Modern Folk Devils: Contemporary Constructions of Evil*, eds. Frederiksen, Martin Demant and Ida Harboe Knudsen, 135–156. Helsinki: Helsinki University Press.

- Tóth, Lilla, György Lengyel and Borbála Göncz. 2025. "Covid-19 as a tool to target democratic institutions and values: The case of Hungary." *Journal of Comparative Politics* 18 (1): 121–143.
- Vachudova, Milada Anna. 2020. "Ethnopolitism and democratic backsliding in central Europe." *East European Politics* 36 (3): 318–340.
- Van Hiel, Alain, Emma Onraet, Bostyn Dries H., et al. 2020. "A meta-analytic integration of research on the relationship between right-wing ideological attitudes and aggressive tendencies." *European Review of Social Psychology* 31 (1): 183–221.
- Vučković Juroš, Tanja, Ivana Dobrotić and Sunčica Flego. 2020. "The rise of the anti-gender movement in Croatia and the 2013 marriage referendum." *Europe-Asia Studies* 72 (9): 1523–1553.
- Windisch, Beth. 2023. "A downward spiral: the role of hegemonic masculinity in lone actor terrorism." *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 46 (12): 2363–2380.
- Zimmerman, Shannon. 2024. "The ideology of incels: Misogyny and victimhood as justification for political violence." *Terrorism and Political Violence* 36 (2): 166–179.

NELIBERALNA STALIŠČA IN UPRAVIČEVANJE NASILJA: VLOGA MIZOGINIJ PRI SPODKOPAVANJU DEMOKRACIJE

V zadnjih letih je ponoven vzpon avtoritarnih teženj in političnega ekstremizma v Srednji in Vzhodni Evropi spodbudil obnovljeno znanstveno pozornost do sociokulturnih dejavnikov, ki vzdržujejo takšne ideologije. Med njimi se je mizoginija izkazala kot pomemben ideološki spremljevalec avtoritarizma in političnega nasilja. Prispevek preučuje preplet mizoginije in političnega radikalizma na podlagi podatkov iz raziskave Joint European Values Study/World Values Survey (EVS/WVS 2024). Ugotovitve kažejo, da je mizoginija pomemben napovednik političnega nasilja v petih državah ter v združenem regionalnem modelu, medtem ko podpora vojaški oblasti dosledno korelira z nasilnimi političnimi stališči. Demokratične vrednote so negativno povezane s političnim nasiljem. Sociodemografski dejavniki, kot sta spol in starost, kažejo omejene in kontekstualno pogojene učinke, medtem ko raven dohodka ni pomemben napovednik. Rezultati poudarjajo konvergenco spolnih predsodkov in avtoritarizma kot destabilizacijske sile v postkomunističnih demokracijah, ki prispeva k demokratičnemu nazadovanju in družbenopolitični polarizaciji.

Ključne besede: mizoginija; protispolna mobilizacija; avtoritarizem; spolni predsodki; postkomunistične družbe; politično nasilje.